

Repurposing of electric vehicle batteries for second life stationary applications in residential photovoltaic systems: an environmental and economic sustainability assessment

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List of acronyms

BEV: Battery Electric Vehicle

DOD: Depth of discharge

ESU: Energy Storage Unit

EV: Electric vehicle

LCA: Life Cycle Assessment

LCC: Life Cycle Costing

LCEV: Light Commercial Electric Vehicle

LET: Lifetime Energy Throughput

LFP: Lithium Iron Phosphate (batteries)

NMC: Nickel Manganese Cobalt (batteries)

PHEV: Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle

PV: photovoltaic

SOH: State of health

Abstract

The increasing adoption of electric vehicles (EV) raises concerns about battery sustainability, highlighting the need for efficient repurposing strategies. This study assesses the economic and environmental feasibility of repurposing EV batteries for stationary energy storage units (ESU) in residen-

tial photovoltaic (PV) systems in Italy. A life cycle cost (LCC) and life cycle assessment (LCA) approach is applied to compare repurposed and new battery systems, introducing Lifetime Energy Throughput (LET) as a metric for evaluating second-life performance. Results indicate that repurposing remains economically viable if new battery prices stay above €150–200/kWh. However, profitability is highly sensitive to market prices and design constraints, such as limiting depth of discharge (DOD) to 50% for prolonged secondary lifetimes, which increases ESU size by 66%. Automation and economies of scale—including robotic disassembly and standardized testing—could offset declining repurposed battery profitability, reducing disassembly time by 20–50% and labor costs by 49%. Policy incentives, such as VAT reductions or CO₂ taxes, could further enhance competitiveness of circular business models and increase attractiveness to customers. From an environmental perspective, LCA results show that repurposed batteries outperform new batteries across all impact categories, reducing carbon footprint by 50–90%. A digital battery passport, mandated by upcoming EU regulations, could facilitate repurposing by improving State of Health (SOH) assessment and enabling data-sharing among stakeholders. In conclusion, while repurposing EV batteries presents significant economic and environmental benefits, sustained viability depends on policy support, automation, and standardized protocols to optimize costs and ensure market competitiveness.

1. Introduction

Responding to a growing environmental awareness from part of the civil society and the need to decarbonize the European economy and become increasingly independent from foreign fossil fuel imports, the electric vehicle (EV) market is booming. This market has been growing strongly in Europe, overtaking the Chinese market by the end of 2020 (1.4 vs. 1.34 million vehicles) (Perkins 2021). One of the main barriers to the widespread adoption of EVs is the high price of batteries (Neubauer et al. 2015a). Provided that EVs are charged with renewable energy sources to effectively lower the environmental burden of such transport means compared to internal combustion engine vehicles (Bobba et al. 2018a), the main environmental hotspot for most impact categories would be the battery (Ahmadi et al. 2017). The reuse, repurposing and (where these options are not available) recycling of batteries is, therefore, a critical aspect of the economic feasibility and environmental sustainability of EVs. Some experimental projects have been tested to demonstrate such examples of circular economy, since battery packs at the end of their traction life still have 50-80% of residual capacity and could therefore be used later in selected static applications, e.g. as power storage unit in a solar photovoltaic (PV) system (Assunção et al. 2016, Neubauer et al. 2012; Lacey et al. 2013; Bobba et al. 2018b).

The European Union (EU) is working to relocate battery cell production to Europe, to reduce dependency on Asian suppliers. It is paramount to understand what factors determine the environmental sustainability of battery reuse and refurbish processes, as well as the parameters that influence

their economic viability. This is necessary to close the open material loop system of the current battery life cycle, which is the main goal behind the recent Battery Regulation (European Commission 2023).

Several initiatives have been implemented to repurpose batteries, such as Eaton's xStorage, a residential Energy Storage Unit (ESU) built from automotive batteries of the Nissan Leaf EV¹. The domestic version, xStorage Home, is sold at € 3,500 (price without VAT or installation costs) for a nominal capacity of 4.2 kWh. The company Forsee Power developed a similar business model, re-using its 'spent' batteries sold for electromobility solutions in stationary second-life applications². Other similar pilot projects have been undertaken by car manufacturers such as BMW and Tesla, described in the European SASLAB project report (Bobba et al. 2018b).

A number of life cycle assessment (LCA) studies on battery repurposing viability for different stationary applications have also been carried out (Ahmadi et al. 2017; Bobba et al. 2018a; Yang et al. 2020). Case studies of repurposed batteries applied to the residential PV sector in Spain have investigated an optimal storage size that could reduce the cost of electricity for users through linear programming (Saez-de-Ibarra et al. 2015). A techno-economic analysis of repurposed EV batteries for domestic PV systems in Portugal found over 10 years of secondary lifetime, a reduction of 78-82% of energy injected to the grid and payback times of 6-9.5 years, highlighting the technical benefits and economic viability of such applications programming (Alfaro-Algaba and Ramirez 2020). An economic analysis of battery repurposing based on laboratory tests has been published too, where the testing and disassembly times of a battery pack of a commercial electric car are reported (Rallo et al. 2020). In the US Renewable Energy Laboratory, the ageing of batteries used in EVs have been simulated taking into account climatic conditions and different driving styles, to estimate the sustainability of repurposing batteries for stationary second life applications (Neubauer and Pesaran 2011; Eyer et al. 2012). These models were subsequently used to map the most cost-effective potential applications, to identify the main limitations and barriers, and then to assess the economic viability of such a business model in the US (Neubauer et al. 2015b).

The main limitations and issues for adequate EV battery repurposing as found in the performed literature review are outlined here:

¹ www.eaton.com

² <https://www.forseepower.com/press-release/forsee-power-signs-mou-with-stationary-storage-specialist-connected-energy-to-extend-the-use-of-transport-battery-systems-into-second-life-applications-15-11-2021/>

- great variability and heterogeneity of batteries for EV on the market, in terms of configurations, anode-cathode chemistry, electronics and communication protocols (Canals Casals and Amante García 2016);
- absence of legislation standardising testing protocols to minimise health risks (safety protocols);
- batteries designed as a single block for one purpose, i.e. they are not designed for a potential secondary use after their automotive lifetime is over. This requires ad hoc disassembly lines with trained and specialized technicians (high disassembly costs);
- until the new regulation on batteries approved last year (European Commission 2023), there was an important legislative void that facilitated the reuse of batteries. The new regulation forces producers to track batteries put in the market through a Digital Battery Passport. A blockchain perspective has been suggested for sharing key performance battery data, which should streamline repurposing and reduce costs (Terkes et al. 2024);
- absence of a scientific consensus to unambiguously define and measure the health status of used batteries, more commonly called State of Health (SOH). It is one of the most important parameters to determine the full sustainability of repurposing and it is very difficult to estimate a priori without information on batteries' operating conditions during their first lifetime (Ahmadi et al. 2014; Casals et al. 2017; Terkes et al. 2024).
- lack of data or lack of access to existing battery data registries to determine the SOH; most of the necessary battery functioning data is either not recorded or it is not available to other stakeholders than the battery manufacturer for confidentiality reasons (Terkes et al. 2024). This has been addressed by the new battery regulation (European Commission 2023).

In this study, a double-angled sustainability assessment has been carried out, analysing together the economic viability and the environmental sustainability (through LCC and LCA, respectively) of modern automotive battery repurposing for a second life application as energy storage units in domestic PV systems in Italy. The main contributions of this study are:

- i) a detailed, cradle-to-gate LCC analysis adapted to Italy for evaluating the business case of repurposing different EV battery types in a European context;
- ii) the introduction of lifetime energy throughput (LET), a simplified metric proposal to adequately compare repurposed and new battery systems energy performance in LCA and LCC;
- iii) a technically-equivalent comparison of the environmental performance of repurposed EV batteries for domestic PV systems with new battery systems.

The study includes a sensitivity analysis for the LCC (pressure testing the model and economic feasibility with less favourable conditions of critical repurposing parameters like future battery prices) and LCA (checking the assessment results with different battery chemistries).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Methodology

In the last years, LCA has become the most internationally recognized and widespread methodology for carrying out comprehensive environmental sustainability assessments of commercial products and services. LCA has also gone mainstream in many industrial applications for product footprinting and environmental product declarations used in business-to-business and business-to-consumer communications. LCA is also the backbone and reference methodology in key European policies, such as the renewable energy directive (European Commission 2018), the recommendations on product environmental footprint communications (European Commission 2013), the green taxonomy for sustainable investments (European Commission 2020) and in the proposal for a directive on green claims³. Most standards and policies typically refer to and follow the principles and requirements set out in the main LCA standards (ISO 2006a, b). These define four steps to carry out an LCA study: i) Goal and scope definition, ii) Life Cycle Inventory, iii) Life Cycle Impact Assessment, and iv) Interpretation and recommendations.

Like LCA, LCC allows identifying the economic hotspots in the life cycle of a product or service. Here a conventional cradle to gate LCC was performed, covering all costs (without considering externalities) associated with the repurposing of used EV batteries. Externalities have been excluded, opting for a conventional LCC, since assessing the economic viability of an EV battery repurposing facility in Italy was an overarching goal of the study and a specific request of the commissioner (see Competing interests). The potential environmental impacts (LCA) and life-cycle costs related to the repurposing of batteries were then compared to those associated with the production of an equivalent new battery system for the selected stationary application.

2.2. Goal and scope definition

2.2.1 Goal

The study focuses on automotive Lithium-Nickel-Manganese-Cobalt (NMC) batteries which are then repurposed as stationary batteries for domestic solar PV systems. The study pursues a double goal: to assess if such a business model is economically feasible and environmentally sound, when compared to a new energy storage system for the selected application. For those economically viable business cases, the cost savings in the value chain are estimated, both on the EV and PV system

³ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-directive-green-claims_en

sides, quantifying possible cost reductions from the sale of used batteries in one hand, and the cost reduction of domestic PV systems with repurposed batteries instead of new ones, in the other hand.

2.2.2 Assessed batteries

The repurposed system consists of used EV battery modules that still hold a minimum energy storage capacity. Considered batteries for repurposing come from different commercial EV models: Battery Electric Vehicles (BEV), Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEV) and Light Commercial Electric Vehicles (LCEV). Their technical specifications can be seen in Table 1. Used batteries are tested, discarding the packs and modules that do not fulfil minimum SOH requirements (SOH < 0.8). Reusable batteries are disassembled to their modules and re-assembled with additional parts into new battery systems of different sizes for the selected stationary application.

The reference system is a new NMC battery designed for a grid-connected domestic PV system. This system design is meant to increase the self-consumption capacity of households, thereby increasing energy production from renewable sources and reducing the demand for electricity production from the grid (Bobba et al. 2018b). A different chemistry in the reference battery system is considered in the sensitivity analysis (see section 3.2.1.1).

Table 1. Characteristics and technical specifications of the batteries and modules considered taken from publicly available information. They represent batteries used in popular EVs on the market. Brand names and models have been anonymized.

	BEV	PHEV	LCEV
Battery capacity [kWh]	52	10.7	74
Number of battery modules	12	5	16
Number of battery packs	1	1	2
Battery weight (kg)	326	94	260
Battery chemistry	NMC	NMC	NMC
Average capacity per module (kWh)	4.3	2.1	2.3

2.2.3 Geographical and temporal scope

The study focuses on Italy and uses national battery sale statistics (2010 to 2019) and EV sale projections to 2030⁴ to estimate the total volume of intercepted batteries for repurposing. This is used during the LCC to estimate the repurposing site dimension and related costs like labour.

⁴ Provided by COBAT

2.2.4 System boundaries

The system boundaries for both battery systems end at the factory gate. However, the use and final disposal stages of both battery systems are expected to be very similar in terms of costs and impacts, since the functional unit has been defined in a way to make both the repurposed and the new battery systems equivalent in terms of the energy service provided to households (see section 2.2.5). Moreover, the domestic energy demand, the PV system with its electrical installation and the national grid where the batteries are installed are assumed to be identical in both systems. Likewise, the costs and impacts of the end of life of both battery systems are expected to be similar, since the materials and components are the same, as well as the country where the batteries are installed and disposed of. Hence, despite both the LCC and LCA are, strictly speaking, “cradle-to-gate” analysis, the results of the study can be considered representative of the full life cycle of such energy storage systems, i.e. “cradle-to-grave” (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. System boundaries of the analysed energy storage systems: raw material extraction and processing (reference system), used battery collection and transport to facility (repurposed system); new battery parts manufacturing and assembly (reference system), used battery testing, disassembly, module selection, and assembly with new parts (repurposed system).

2.2.5 Functional Unit

To compare the reference system with the repurposed system, we define the functional unit through two energy performance indicators. This is necessary to cover two basic requirements of the energy service that such battery systems must fulfil (i.e. total energy provided to the household) during a

day and during their lifetimes. The first parameter is the effective storage capacity over time, $K_{eff}(t)$, of the battery systems and covers the energy service that these provide on a daily basis:

$$K_{eff}(t) = K_0 \cdot SOH_t \cdot DOD \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

Where K_0 is the nominal storage capacity (kWh), SOH_t is the battery's state of health at a specific time and DOD is the maximum depth of discharge. For repurposed batteries, the initial SOH_{t_0} is a key technical prerequisite for their usability in second life applications and it is set at 80% (Neubauer et al. 2012). The DOD is capped at 70% through the new battery management system to have a prolonged secondary lifetime that is equivalent, or as close as possible, to the new battery in terms of duration and energy storage capacity (Assunção et al. 2016).

The second energy performance indicator defines the reference flow of the functional unit and it is based on the present value of throughput method to cover the lifetime aspect of the energy service of batteries (Neubauer et al. 2012). We define the lifetime energy throughput (LET) as the cumulative energy storage capacity over the second-life, taking into account the battery degradation over time (see Equation 2):

$$LET = \int_{c_0}^{c_{max}} SOH_{initial} \cdot DOD \cdot K_{eff}(c) \cdot dc \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

The LET encompasses the total amount of energy that batteries can accumulate and give back to the households during their lifetime, depending on their SOH, nominal capacity and maximum DOD by design. Simplifying the storage capacity over time $K_{eff}(c)$ as a function of the number of charge-discharge cycles (Ellingsen et al. 2014):

$$K_{eff}(c) = K_0 - K_0 \cdot (\delta \cdot c) \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

Where δ is the battery degradation index, we can now combine Equation 2 and 3 to get the LET. Since modelling an accurate battery degradation was out of scope of this study, this linear model with conservative assumption is deemed sufficient to approximate the real LET of the batteries, as similarly done in other studies (Neubauer et al. 2012). The degradation index and the amount of maximum cycles that the batteries can perform are determined by the operating conditions, such as DOD and discharge power, which are controlled by the battery management system. Hence, by integrating Equation 3 with the application conditions (i.e. DOD and $SOH_{initial}$ of 80%), we obtain the formula that defines the LET of repurposed batteries as a function of K_0 , δ , c :

$$LET = SOH_{initial} \cdot DOD \cdot K_0 \cdot \left[\left(c - \frac{\delta \cdot c^2}{2} \right) \right] \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

Where c is the number of estimated cycles that batteries are expected to perform at the design DOD. For new batteries c is assumed to be 5000, while c is assumed to be 4500 cycles in repurposed batteries, based on the results of a study using a non-linear battery degradation model for domestic PV

systems in Portugal (same application, same DOD and similar ambient conditions as this study) (Assunção et al. 2016). Taking the parametric values of this study, the degradation index δ is hence linearly approximated as:

$$\delta = \frac{(SOH_{initial} - SOH_{final})}{c} \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

The differences between new and repurposed batteries in terms of SOH, storage capacity and LET, have hence been addressed through the modularity of ESU. Hence, resulting ESU configurations are about 1.8 times bigger than their new counterpart reference battery systems, as they depart with a $SOH_{initial}$ of 80% and have a maximum DOD of 70%. For example, a ESU-BEV of 4 modules (17.3 kWh_{nominal}, 9.3 kWh_{effective}, 32.8 kWh_{LET}) is compared to the new battery of 9.8 kWh_{nominal}, 9.5 kWh_{effective}, 30.0 kWh_{LET}.

The electricity consumption of an average Italian residential unit is 2,154 kWh year⁻¹, or 5.9 kWh day⁻¹, ranging from 3.2 to 9.4 kWh day⁻¹ (Besagni et al. 2020). Based on this range of measured household consumption for Italy, repurposed batteries are reconfigured into ESUs of different sizes by combining several modules to get an effective storage capacity within that range and as close as possible to existing commercial batteries. For additional details see section S1.4 in the Supplementary Materials and Tables therein for all the technical characteristics and parameter values used for all batteries.

2.2.6 End of life modelling approach

A cut-off modelling approach was followed for the reused battery modules, i.e. repurposed batteries are free of any upstream environmental burden. This modelling choice is tested in the sensitivity analysis (section 3.2.1), through the circular footprint formula for the LCA part, while a used battery price is calculated for the LCC part (section 3.1.1) and tested in a separate sensitivity analysis (section 3.1.3).

2.3. Life Cycle Inventory

The main characteristics of the batteries and modules considered for this study are shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the study is based on the following assumptions:

- i) The volume of intercepted batteries in the Italian market for repurposing is considered to be 75% of the total available each year in the period analysed (2020-2030)⁵. Batteries that

⁵ Source: COBAT data

could be damaged are labelled as dangerous by the dealer and not collected for repurposing. Furthermore, a 10% of the collected batteries are assumed to be discarded after the testing phase. Discarded batteries are assumed to go directly to disposal and are not paid to the owners.

- ii) Repurposed batteries are limited to a DOD of 70% to ensure the longest possible second life (Lacey et al.; Neubauer and Pesaran 2011; Ellingsen et al. 2014)⁶. This allows the number of cycles to be extended and the degradation rate of used batteries to be reduced.
- iii) Used batteries have a $SOH_{initial}$ of 80%. Repurposed batteries are at the end of their second life when they reach a SOH of 30%, which is assumed to occur after 4500 full cycles at the imposed 70% DOD, based on a study that estimated 4200 to 4800 cycles remaining in the same secondary-life application with a non-linear, multi-variable battery degradation model (Assunção et al. 2016).
- iv) New batteries reach the end of their life at a SOH of 30%, which is assumed to occur after 5000 full cycles at nearly full DOD (Assunção et al. 2016)..
- v) If the repurposing of batteries is profitable, the value of used batteries is greater than zero and therefore they are purchased from the owners at a designated price (to be estimated).
- vi) To estimate the purchase price of used batteries, the capital costs are amortized over 5 years, considering an internal rate of return (IRR) of 5%.

For the collection phase of the used batteries, it is considered that the new plant will be located in the area of Bologna (centre north) and that the trucks will cover an average distance of about 300 km (average distance between Bologna and the main Italian cities, such as Genoa, Turin, Milan, Rome). The system has been designed parametrically, i.e. based on the volume of incoming batteries. Due to feasibility constraints, the system was designed for an initial battery volume equivalent to 150,000 kWh year⁻¹ of storage capacity, i.e. 75% of the total flow expected for 2026. The expected volume of batteries for 2030 is an order of magnitude greater than expected for 2026; the size of the plant, and therefore of the business, is multiplied by 10 in just 5 years⁷. To calculate the plant size, the parametric model of Neubauer et al. (2015) was followed. The plant area is calculated from the number of offices needed (for managers), the area needed for workstations for testing, assembly and disassembly, the

⁶ According to the modelling of Casals et al., 2017, for a used battery with an initial SOH of 80%, a maximum DOD of 50%, and a final SOH of 60% (in stationary application as a battery in a PV system), such an ESU would have a second life of 8 years, while in Bobba's model, Podias et al., 2018, it is estimated a second life of 4 years for a second life battery with a DOD of 80%. In Ellingsen et al. (2014) the change is reported on the maximum cycles depending on the DOD of work, provided by an NMC battery manufacturer (1000 cycles at 100% DOD, 5000 cycles at DOD 50%)

⁷ Specifically, the estimated flow is equal to 146,052 kWh/year for 2026.

area for the conveyor belt, the storage shelves for batteries and ESU and a space to manoeuvre forklifts. Thus, the size of the plant will be approximately 3000 m², with 44% of the area destined to the BEV production line, 21% to PHEVs and 35% to LCEVs. The plant has a land cost of 100 €/m² and a cost of 350 €/m² for the construction of the site. Taking 2030 as reference year, and according to the volume of batteries estimated, the plant would have a size of 22,570 m² (and a cost of 6.9 M€). The required staff is calculated based on the times from Rallo et al. (2020) and 252 annual working days. The salaries for each category and contractual level were taken from ISTAT⁸. Full details of the life cycle inventory for the collection and repurposing of EV batteries can be found in Supplementary Materials (Section S1).

All the inventory data has been normalized to 1 kWh_{LET} defined as the reference flow (see Section 2.2.5). All the processes related to the Collection, and Testing & Disassembly of the batteries used for repurposing are calculated based on the nominal capacity. This is because these processes are designed according to the size and weight of the used batteries and modules. The available inventory data from Rallo et al. (2020) is referred to the nominal battery capacity too.

The life cycle inventories for the environmental impact assessment of the NMC batteries have been taken from Majeau-Bettez et al. (2011) and Ellingsen et al. (2014), integrating the data from Bobba et al. (2018) where necessary and using Ecoinvent 3.7 as the main database for all background processes. For the full details of costs and resources inventory calculation of each life cycle stage and battery type, we refer to the life cycle inventory Section S1 in the Supplementary Materials.

2.3.1. Calculation of ESU's selling prices

A key cost of repurposing is related to the purchase of used batteries, which in turn represent the potential cost reduction (and added value from a second life application business model) of the EV value chain. This cost results from the fact that used batteries will have a positive value in a viable repurposing business model, provided that a minimum SOH and LET are guaranteed by the dealer. The selling price of the ESU is calculated following the “battery salvage value” approach of Neubauer et al. 2015, as shown in Equation 6:

$$P_{repurposed} = \frac{LET_{used}}{LET_{new}} \cdot P_{new} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

where the P_{new} factor is the price of a stationary battery of similar performance and characteristics. The price of stationary batteries for the period 2026 – 2030 was estimated from 2020 and 2024 market

⁸ <https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/retribuzioni>

price data and extrapolating linearly until 2030 the seen price decrease. Future price estimates from other sources have proven to be too optimistic, as demonstrated by 2024 data, which contrasts with ambitious projections reported by Bloomberg and others (Logan Goldie-Scot 2019, Steen et al. 2017). Thus, 2024 market prices ranging from 427 to 712 € kWh⁻¹ for stationary batteries were taken, differentiating between sizes (small, medium, big, large), which go down to 299 to 616 € kWh⁻¹ for 2030. ESU selling prices were calculated by multiplying the unitary costs by the usable capacity of repurposed batteries (since these are capped by a 70% maximum DOD to ensure prolonged second lifetimes) to derive the plant revenues from 2026 to 2030. For a summary of the selling prices, please refer to Supplementary Materials (section S2.1, and tables therein).

2.3.2. Calculation of purchase prices of used batteries

The purchase prices for used batteries were calculated iteratively through the net present value (NPV) of the plant, as the acquisition costs of used batteries were the only unknown in the equation that represents the financial ambition of the project (see equation 7):

$$\sum(CapitalCosts_{t=0}) = \sum_{t=1}^{t=5}(Revenues_t - Expenses_t) \cdot (1 + IRR)^{-t} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

Where the IRR is the Internal Rate of Return and "t" is the amortization period, assumed here to be 5% and 5 years, respectively (premise viii). On the left side of the equation are capital costs, i.e., the initial investment needed for the year 2026 (equipment, land, facility). On the right is the sum of the net cash flow for a period of 5 successive years (2026 – 2030).

To obtain the maximum purchase prices of used batteries implies satisfying:

- i) A positive NPV;
- ii) a final repurposed ESU cost lower than the calculated selling price in the previous step.

With the battery salvage values calculated, the total cost of repurposing is obtained by adding indirect costs to cover insurance costs (3% of direct costs), general and administrative costs (5% of direct costs), ESU guarantee costs (5% of revenues), and Research and Development (3% of revenues), as suggested in Neubauer et al. (2015). All the details on ESU's repurposing costs (unit costs in €/kWh, total costs in €/ESU and selling prices in €/ESU) for all battery types can be seen in section S2.2 of the Supplementary Materials and tables therein.

2.4. Impact Assessment

The Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) is finally carried out to characterize the modelled inventories for each battery system in terms of contributions to a recognized set of environmental impact categories. In this study, the Environmental Footprint v3 method was chosen. The assessment was carried out using the Simapro Analyst 9.1 software with Ecoinvent 3.7 as the main background database.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Life Cycle Costing results

3.1.1. EV batteries' salvage value

Table 2 shows the battery salvage values for the three analysed battery types (BEV, PHEV and LCEV). These represent the maximum potential cost reduction in the battery value chain (Neubauer and Pesaran 2011). Battery salvage values were calculated iteratively, maximizing their value by calculating ESU's selling price with projected new stationary battery prices from 2026 to 2030 and expected LET performance (see Section 2.3.2).

Table 2. Maximum purchase price of used batteries. Iteration results computed to get to a near-zero project NPV (IRR of 5%, $t = 5$ years) with integer battery salvage values (no decimals considered in the iterations).

	BEV	PHEV	LCEV
Used battery salvage value (€ kWh ⁻¹)	75	62	98
Buying price, whole used battery	€ 3,900	€ 663	€ 7,252 [§]
NPV	M€ 192	M€ 163	M€ 39

[§] Includes 2 battery packs

As shown in Table 3, BEV and LCEV batteries seem to retain a considerable economic value at the end of their automotive life. Calculated NPV for each battery type show that such repurposing business has still a great margin to further adjust ESU (and purchased used battery) prices according to market evolution. With the considered price estimates and assumptions on used batteries' SOH and LET, repurposing of EV batteries as residential energy units could reduce the total cost of a BEV by as much as € 3,900, and by € 7,252 for LCEV. These values fall in the middle of the 44 to 180 \$/kWh market price range found in a comprehensive review of second-life battery applications (Martinez-Laserna et al. 2018). Repurposing of PHEV batteries show lower profitability, as the repurposing process does not change depending on the capacity of the battery pack. Therefore, the production cost weighs more on packs with low capacities. In other words, the smaller the batteries and their modules, the more expensive the unit costs of repurposing gets.

3.1.2. Total repurposing costs

Once the battery salvage values are calculated, total repurposing costs can be derived, which are shown in Figure 2. As can be seen, the most important costs are consumption costs (68%), mainly due to the costs of purchasing used batteries (44% of total). This is followed by indirect costs (16%), collection and personnel costs (7% each). Capital costs are last in order of importance (2%

of total annual costs). Further graphs and tables on consumption and costs can be in the Supplementary Material (section S2.2 “Summary of repurposing costs” and tables therein). These results are aligned with other similar studies (Cready et al. 2003), where main costs were found to be batteries (56%) and labour (13%). A recent review on battery repurposing shows a similar cost distribution, used batteries and labour being the main drivers (Terkes et al. 2024).

Figure 2 Breakdown of total costs for an EV battery repurposing factory in Italy.

3.1.2.1. Benchmarking of repurposed ESU to market batteries

The characteristics of the repurposed ESUs from BEV batteries are presented below according to the number of modules assembled and the LET. Similar tables for PHEV and LCEV can be consulted in Tables S15 and S16 in the SM. As can be seen in Table 3, the results of the analysis indicate that there is a repurposing business case. For PHEV battery types the selling price of some ESU would remain below the battery cost, which means that the profitability of repurposing also follows economies of scale, being low or inexistent for batteries with small modules. The price would still be around 25% of the selling price of the new similar battery (the new 3.3 without VAT, inverter, or installation). Considering also the possible drop in the prices of new batteries reported here in the near future, the repurposed ESUs still maintain a good margin to remain competitive in the field of residential storage for domestic PV systems. Alternatively, Table 4 and Tables S15 and S16 show that there is margin to reduce the selling prices to make repurposed batteries more attractive to consumers, since they are around 1/3 times bigger but have about 23% lower usable capacity and can only provide 80% of LET compared to new battery systems. Equivalent energy storage capacity and LET performance to new

batteries of repurposed ESUs (e.g. 5 modules ESU-BEV, see Table 3) would imply 67% larger sizes than their counterparts.

Table 3 Comparison of performance and selling prices ESU – BEV with market prices for similar new batteries (estimated prices for 2026 of 309 to 561 € kWh⁻¹).

Battery configuration	Nameplate capacity (kWh)	Usable energy (kWh)	Unit Cost (€/kWh)	Total ESU Cost (€)	2026 selling price (€)	LET (MWh)	LET difference
1 module	4.3	2.4	213	922	1361	8.2	81%
2 modules	8.7	4.9	186	1608	1755	16.4	82%
3 modules	13.0	7.3	177	2295	2305	24.6	82%
4 modules	17.3	9.7	172	2981	3003	32.8	82%
5 modules	21.7	12.1	169	3668	4565	41.0	103% ^a
New 3.3	3.3	3.2	712	-	2286	10.1	
New 6.5	6.5	6.3	459	-	2857	19.9	
New 9.8	9.8	9.5	406	-	3792	30.0	
New 13	13.0	12.6	395	-	4891	39.8	

^a Compared to New 13 kWh battery

The competitiveness of the final ESU prices depend strongly on the final price of new similar batteries and the size of the packs and modules. The BEV and LCEV business scenarios, with bigger battery packs and modules, are more likely to be profitable while PHEV battery repurposing remains more problematic (see the sensitivity analysis section 3.1.3).

To illustrate the application of the LCC performed, two ESU from repurposed BEV were chosen, based on the average energy needs of an Italian household, which according to the recent analysis by Besagni et al. (2020) should cover an average daily consumption of 5.9 kWh. The energy needs could therefore be covered with a PV system connected to a new battery with a nominal capacity of 6.5 kWh (the actual capacity is 90%), or a first ESU – BEV of 2 modules (8.7 kWh nominal, 4.9 kWh useful). Under the assumed conditions and assumptions, both ESU would have similar overall prices to the new reference battery, aligned with their technical characteristics (see Table 5).

Table 4 Price comparison and performance of ESU and reference battery

Battery characteristics	ESU – BEV (2 modules)	ESU – BEV (3 modules)	Reference battery

Nominal capacity (kWh)	8.7	13.0	6.5
Usable energy at initial capacity (kWh)	6.9	10.4	6.3
Usable energy at design DOD (kWh)	4.9	7.3	6.2
Estimated LET (MWh)	16.4	24.6	19.9
Cost, at factory gate (€)	1,608	2,295	-
2026 selling price (without VAT, inverter and installation)	€ 1,755	€ 2,305	€ 2,900[†]

[†] Taking a 2024 market price. A € 2,000 inverter cost that is included in the original price (€ 3,900) was assumed to estimate the comparable price.

3.1.3. Sensitivity analysis of LCC

Having considered three different battery types, each with different module and pack sizes, a good range of variability has already been covered in terms of scenario analysis. The most critical parameters for the economic profitability of a repurposing business are:

- a. The dimensions of the battery packs and their modules;
- b. Future prices of new reference batteries;
- c. SOH of used batteries;
- d. Maximum DOD of repurposed batteries, capped by design to ensure acceptable second lifetimes

As argued by previously cited references, used batteries should have an acceptable SOH for their repurposing to be economically viable. The specific SOH of recovered batteries needs to be assessed individually before starting with any repurposing activities. If the assessed SOH does not reach a pre-determined threshold (here set at 0.8, as per cited literature), recovered batteries will be discarded and sent to recycling.

Given the increasing importance of electromobility and the battery market in general, future prices for new automotive batteries in the next 10 years are taken from a Bloomberg study (Logan Goldie-Scot 2019). Pressure testing the model with less favourable conditions (new battery prices of 150 \$ kWh⁻¹, the sensitivity analysis shows that repurposing EV batteries may only be viable for big packs (capacity greater than 40 kWh), leaving out of the business case small batteries from PHEV (see Table 5). Further constraining the maximum DOD in repurposed batteries to 50% to ensure a long secondary lifetime (over 8 years) (Casals et al. 2017), implies bigger ESU for the similar storage capacities and LET to the reference batteries, thus higher costs too. In this case, the used battery salvage values drop significantly as well, but all EV battery types showed positive NPV and higher

selling prices to total ESU costs. Combining both factors, there would be no repurposing business case for none of the EV batteries.

Table 5. New battery salvage value estimates based on lower new battery prices and lower DOD_{Max} for repurposed batteries.

	<i>Ambitious price scenario^a</i>			<i>DOD_{Max} 50%</i>		
	BEV	PHEV	LCEV	BEV	PHEV	LCEV
Used battery salvage value (€ kWh ⁻¹)	10	0	9	38	5	45
Buying price, whole used battery	€ 520	-	€ 666 [§]	€ 1,976	€ 54	€ 3,330 [§]
NPV	M€ 43	M€ 7	M€ 52	M€ 266	M€ 56	M€ 196

^a New battery price reaches 150 \$ kWh⁻¹

[§] Includes 2 battery packs

As it can be seen, selling prices would decrease dramatically, and so the repurposing unit costs (as the acquisition of used batteries is one of the main cost drivers). For PHEV batteries the business would not be profitable anymore. BEV and LCEV results show a good margin to run viable repurposing businesses for these battery types, although the cost reduction of for EV would be limited. For The reduction in the profitability of repurposed batteries due to a significant decrease of new batteries, could be offset by efficiency improvements in the form of economies of scale (e.g. reduced transport and component costs). Further cost reductions could be expected from standardization of communication protocols and SOH determination through the digital passport, disassembly safety protocols, battery design that eases disassembly, robotization and general improvements from learning. A protocol for a fast and safe disassembly could substantially reduce the time involved through automation with modular robotic systems with artificial intelligence. In addition to reducing disassembly and assembly times (from 20% to 50%, depending on the complexity of the process), automation would also lead to further savings in personnel costs because it would reduce the number of technicians needed (a 49% of the labour cost in this study). Finally, a reduced VAT on repurposed products or business activities or a CO₂ tax could also give an additional incentive to such repurposing battery systems, as they would become more competitive than the new ones and would support solar energy storage (which is CO₂ free).

3.2. Life Cycle Assessment results

The environmental footprint results for the reference system vary, decreasing with the storage capacity of new NMC batteries. This means that the environmental performance of new batteries, i.e. the sum of impacts per kWh of storage, decreases with their size. The main reading of the results obtained, also in line with other studies in the literature, is that the environmental footprints of repurposed

battery systems remain significantly lower than the baseline ones for practically all the impact categories analysed (see graphs and tables in Supplementary Material). This means that second life ESU have multiple and significant environmental benefits compared to new batteries. The battery type with a better environmental performance is the BEV (i.e. the largest battery pack with larger modules), followed by the LCEV and the PHEV (which is still better than the new more performing NMC battery, the 13 kWh). Figure 3 graphically illustrates the Climate Change impact results for the storage systems analysed. Repurposed battery impacts vary according to the battery type but, unlike new storage systems, their impacts are constant in terms of battery size (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 Results of the calculation of the climate-altering impact of the storage systems analysed

Considering the borderline cases of the two systems compared (i.e. the PHEV, the least performing, and the new NMC of 13 kWh, the best performing of the new ones), the repurposing of the batteries would in any case be an excellent alternative from an environmental point of view, under the conditions and assumptions described above. Further results concerning the comparison of environmental performances of all batteries in other categories are shown in Supplementary Material, Section S3.

3.2.1. Sensitivity analysis

Similar to the analysis carried out previously, the study already covers a good range of scenario analysis in terms of battery types, pack and module sizes. Two important additional aspects have been considered for the sensitivity analysis, namely the chemistry (and thus the LET performance) of the new battery system, and the end-of-life allocation of used batteries for repurposing. For the battery chemistry, a LFP one was modelled (more common in stationary applications) as a reference system. The end-of-life allocation was changed from the polluter pays or cut-off modeling approach to the circular footprint formula, which considers the residual economic value of the recycled or reused materials as criterion to allocate upstream and downstream burdens.

3.2.1.1. New LFP chemistry batteries as a reference system

We focus here on an alternative scenario for the reference system, where we model a storage system with new batteries of LFP chemistry instead of NMC. LFP batteries have a lower energy density than NMCs, which are more widely used more used in automotive today, but they have longer longevity and therefore some manufacturers choose this chemistry for stationary applications. The technical specifications from a manufacturer were used for the correct description of the system and to complete the related inventory, adapted from the inventory of NMC batteries. To simplify, the only component modified was the main cathode material, taking LiFePO_4 instead of LiNixCoyMnzO_2 .

Inventory data reported in the previously cited LCA studies (Majeau-Bettez et al. 2011; Ellingsen et al. 2014) were also taken to model the production of the LFP cathode and its supply chain ending with the production of LiFePO_4 , not present in the Ecoinvent 3.7 database. Figure 4 illustrates the single result of the Climate Change impact category for the analysed storage systems (new NMC and LFP batteries, and repurposed batteries). As it can be seen, the overall conclusions do not change with the new battery chemistry. Additional graphs and tables concerning the sensitivity analysis are shown in Supplementary Materials, Section S3.

The use of LFP batteries in the reference system would change the end-of-life (EoL) impacts and revenues, compared to repurposed NMC batteries, since the latter are known to have much higher material recovery rates than the former (Picatoste et al. 2024). As demonstrated by the analysis performed in this study, NMC batteries are more resource efficient than LFP batteries, thus including the EoL stage would further increase the shown environmental benefits of repurposed NMC batteries compared to new LFP ones.

Figure 4 Results of the calculation of the climate-altering impact of the storage systems analysed.

3.2.1.2. Circular Economy allocation criterion

Another allocation can be performed using Circular Footprint Formula (CFF) which balances the environmental burdens between primary and secondary products. Following this methodological approach, the environmental burden of the production of the new NMC batteries was distributed between the first useful life (automotive use) and the second life (ESU for PV system) through the A factor. As we have no other indices that can measure the possible quality of repurposed batteries, we took the SOH as an approximation for A⁹. Consequently, the impacts of repurposed batteries are considered there as follows (Equation 1), similar to the approach followed in (Bobba et al. 2018a).

Equation 1 CFF formula to allocate the environmental loads of the production of new batteries (and the virgin raw materials related to them) between new and repurposed batteries

$$I_{repurposing_{TOTAL}} = I_{repurposing_{processes}} + (1 + A) \cdot I_{new} + A \cdot I_{EoL}$$

Where A is equal to the SOH of the batteries in this sensitivity analysis (i.e. 0.8), whereas A = 1 for the analysis performed previously (cut-off results). A selection of the results for the sensitivity analysis with the allocation criterion of "Circular Economy" is presented. As could be expected, and as seen in Figure 5, environmental results increase with this allocation criterion. However, the environmental footprint of repurposed batteries remains lower than that of new NMC 6.5 batteries. In the case of the ESU with PHEV batteries, this would remain similar to the environmental footprint of the new LFP 6.6 battery, and therefore worse than the ESU with new batteries >6.6 kWh of storage. Further results are shown in Supplementary Materials, section S3.

⁹ In the PEF, an A of 0.5 is recommended for unknown situations or where the market situation is balanced.

Figure 5 Sensitivity of climate change results (gCO₂eq/kWh_{LET}) to end-of-life modeling approaches (Cut-off and CFF) for the main energy storage systems analysed: repurposed (BEV, LCEV and PHEV) and new (NMC and LFP chemistry) batteries.

4. Conclusions

Cradle-to-gate costs and environmental impacts of repurposed EV batteries for domestic solar PV systems' have been assessed and compared to those of new batteries. The technical equivalence of repurposed energy storage units (ESU) with new battery systems was addressed in two complementary ways. First, by introducing the potential lifetime energy throughput (LET), as main service provided by the batteries, in the definition of the functional unit. Secondly, by assuming a minimum initial state of health (SOH) of used batteries of 80% and by capping their maximum depth of discharge (DOD) during their second-life application to 70%. These repurposing conditions implied assembling used battery modules into ESU that are 30% larger than new ones (or 66% larger, if DOD_{max} is constrained to 50% to ensure long secondary lifetimes). This size increase may deter potential customers, as space constraints in domestic settings can be a limiting factor. However, it is necessary to ensure equivalent functional units, i.e. similar usable storage capacities and LET in both systems over a comparable lifetime. Customers' preferences can be shaped if the prices of repurposed ESU are significantly lower than new battery systems, which can be facilitated with the right environmental taxation policies. The forementioned core assumptions enabled the calculation of LET using an innovative and simplified approach, which, in turn, allowed for the comparison of the environmental and economic performance of repurposed ESUs. Since repurposed batteries are assembled using individual modules (with fixed capacities) from previous EV battery packs, the resulting ESUs did not always perfectly match new reference batteries in terms of storage capacity and LET. To correct this dissimilarity of the basic energy service provided by both systems, a "battery salvage

value” was incorporated to calculate both the purchasing price of used batteries and the selling price of repurposed ESU. The selling price of repurposed ESU were calculated by multiplying the usable capacity (i.e. nominal capacity adjusted with the SOH and maximum DOD_{max}) of batteries with the LET ratio (LET_{used}/LET_{new}) and the estimated market prices for new stationary batteries.

In general, the costs reported here can be considered in line with other literature studies (Neubauer et al. 2012, Steen et al. 2017, Martinez-Laserna et al. 2018). From the results of the economic analysis performed it was observed that the repurposing costs are dominated by the purchase of used batteries (battery salvage values), which amount to 43% of the total annual costs for the year 2026. These costs are followed in importance by indirect costs (18% of total), collection and transport costs (9%) and labour costs (9%). Calculated battery salvage values of used EV batteries show a significant potential of repurposing to reduce EV costs – currently one of the main barriers for their widespread adoption: €3,900 (or 75 €/kWh) for BEV, €663 (or 62 €/kWh) for PHEV and €7,252 (or 98 €/kWh) for LCEV. However, the economic feasibility of repurposing is highly sensitive to future market prices. If the most optimistic future price projections are achieved by 2030 for new batteries (at 150 \$/kWh), used battery salvage values can be much lower or inexistent: €520 (or 10 €/kWh) for BEV, no value for PHEV and €666 (or 9 €/kWh) for LCEV. This would result in a low cost reduction potential from repurposing for the EV value chain (10 €/kWh). Imposing a maximum DOD of 50% in repurposed ESU to prolong their secondary lifetimes and to ensure an equivalent energy performance to new batteries, would further reduce the salvage value of used batteries and would make repurposed ESU 67% larger than their new counterparts. If low market prices of new batteries are realized and repurposed batteries need to be constrained to $SOH > 0.8$ and DOD_{max} of 50%, the business case of such a repurposing model vanishes. The decline in repurposed battery profitability due to cheaper new batteries could be offset by economies of scale, standardized protocols, fast and accurate SOH determination with battery information stored in future digital passport. Improved battery designs, and automation, with AI-driven robotic systems could further reduce disassembly time (by 20–50%) and labor costs (by 49%) through decreased reliance on technicians.

From 2027, according to the new European legislation on batteries, car manufacturers will have to incorporate a digital passport and a registry with the key parameters to determine the SOH of the batteries, provided a scientific consensus over a standard definition of SOH is reached. This will save part of the testing phase costs and to derive at delivery the compensation price (salvage value) of used batteries, which may smoothen the existing barriers for repurposing businesses. Comparing the prices of ESU with new batteries, the performed LCC analysis showed that, EV battery repurposing for

domestic PV systems could only be competitive if new battery prices stay above 150-200 \$/kWh. Governments could further incentivise repurposing by giving more margin to reuse and refurbish businesses by reducing tax levies. For example, repurposed products like the ESU analysed in this paper could benefit from a lower VAT (e.g. 10% instead of current 22%) highlight the environmental advantages of circular business models compared to resource-intensive new products, such as batteries. Such policies could facilitate the expansion of renewable energy production and installed capacity, enhancing the self-sufficiency of dwellings, lowering energy bills, and delivering significant environmental benefits. Additionally, they could reduce the country's reliance on strategic resources that may be vulnerable to supply constraints, price surges, disruptions, or geopolitical conflicts.

From the environmental analysis performed by LCA modelling, it is clear that all repurposed battery scenarios (BEV, LCEV and PHEV) demonstrate significantly better environmental profiles than their new NMC and LFP battery reference systems. The environmental footprints calculated using the European Environmental Footprint (EF) v3 methodology, lead to impact reductions in all the categories analyzed ranging from 50% to 90%, which is an order of magnitude of the multiple environmental benefits that such a business could generate. Finally, for the repurposed batteries the environmental hot-spots are concentrated in the new components (the electronic printed circuit board for the battery management system in particular) to be integrated with the modules needed to build the ESU. For the new NMC batteries the hotspots are found in the cathode materials (cobalt extraction and production of the related alloys, such as NiCoMn). The sensitivity analysis of the LCA covered two important methodological choices, such as the battery chemistry reference system (LFP instead of NMC) and allocation criterion used for repurposed batteries. Having LFP batteries in the reference system would further increase the benefits of repurposed NMC batteries, as the latter show much higher material recovery rates at their end-of-life than the former (Picatoste et al. 2024). Applying the circular footprint formula at end-of-life instead of the cut-off or recycled-content criterion reduced the showed environmental benefits but did not change the conclusions, highlighting the important environmental benefits of repurposed NMC batteries compared to new NMC or LFP batteries for stationary applications as domestic PV systems.

A registry system to record the key parameters in the BMS to characterize the batteries at the end of the first life is fundamental. This would allow to determine quickly and with precision the degradation rate and the overall SOH status of used batteries, which enable an accurate calculation of their LET potential and, thus, their salvage value. BMS communication problems with modules from different manufacturers could be expected. To bypass this barrier, battery manufacturers should be obliged to

provide communication protocols, e.g. in the upcoming battery digital passports, to manage the charging and discharging of different modules assembled together in new storage units.

Declarations and statements

Data availability

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request

Competing interests

This study was fully funded by Motus-e, an Italian association that gathers industrial stakeholders from the automotive sector, car manufacturers and researchers to foster electric mobility solutions.

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